

MS Spectra of the known compounds

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■ -Q1: 4.418 min from Sample 2 (YAC-3N) of 24092015.wiff (Turbo Spray)

Max. 1.1e6 cps.

LCMS Spectrum of Tephrowatsin A (21)

■ -Q1: 7.474 min from Sample 5 (YAC-3D) of 24092015.wiff (Turbo Spray)

Max: 9.5e6 cps.

